

TOWARDS UNDERSTANDING AND MODELING IRREVERSIBLE BEHAVIOR OF WOVEN FABRICS UNDER LOADING-UNLOADING BENDING REGIMES

R. Sourki¹, A. S. Milani^{1*}, and R. Vaziri^{1*}

¹ Composites Research Network, The University of British Columbia, Canada

* Abbas Milani (Abbas.Milani@ubc.ca), Reza Vaziri (Reza.Vaziri@ubc.ca)

Keywords: Irreversible behaviour, Woven fabrics, Bending, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

The plethora of previous numerical simulations of woven fabrics has often overlooked the highly multi-scale nature of these materials under out-of-plane bending deformation. In addition, the majority of investigations have utilized the elastic material models such as hyper-elastic and hypo-elastic models [1, 2], which cannot consider the dissipated energy during forming processes under loading-unloading regimes. The observed irreversible behavior of woven fabrics under cyclic conditions can be a result of crimp/undulation, dissipated friction within and between yarns, and fiber twist. In this paper, a numerical model developed at the meso-level is presented in order to investigate anti-plane deformation of a dry thermoplastic woven fabric composite under a loading-unloading bending regime. The effect of yarn material stiffness, crossover friction, and angle of rotation on the resulting nonlinear and irreversible bending response of the fabric is also discussed through design of experiments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Woven fabric composites are among widely utilized materials in modern industrial products. For example, in the last decade, these composites have been increasingly used in primary structural components of aircrafts such as Boeing 777, Boeing 787, and Airbus A350. There are several key aspects that should be considered during the manufacturing (forming) process of woven composites. First, the friction between and within fiber tows/yarns plays a critical role during forming. Furthermore, significant levels of fiber twist and fiber misalignment can lead to a large variability and non-repeatability of forming outcome [3, 4]. In turn, these key factors can result in a non-reversible behavior of the reinforcing fabric during loading-unloading conditions, e.g. those of inflatable woven structures.

A critical aspect of numerical analysis of thermoplastic textile reinforced composites is to understand the effect of in-plane and out-of-plane deformation during 3D forming events. A multi-scale analysis is an indispensable part of such an effort. Previous research has established that the meso-level modeling is a useful tool for studying the effective mechanical properties of fabrics at the macro-level [1, 5]. In the presented study, using the Mullin effect concept, a meso-level numerical analysis is adopted to assess the effect of friction, angle of rotation, and material parameters on the irreversible bending behavior of a typical woven fabric under a full loading-unloading cycle.

2 EXPERIMENTAL: BENDING TESTS

Research into bending characterization methods has a long history and there are numerous published literature on pertinent test methods since the 1930s. Peirce was among the first who studied the fabrics bending stiffness and buckling properties [6]. Several researchers used the same approach and others modified the Peirce method in order to more accurately capture the bending behavior of fabrics [7-9]. Other than Peirce bending test method that is based on the linear theory, there have been other methods and techniques such as Kawabata's Evaluation System (KES) [10] that is capable of capturing the moment-curvature curves under cyclic loadings; however, it has been reported that this device is not optimized for composite reinforcements or pre-pregs [9]. Later, Martin et al. [11] used a V-bend apparatus to obtain the bending behavior of thermoplastic composite materials (see [9, 12] for a more detailed review).

Figure 1: (a) The custom bending device to measure the varying bending stiffness of fabrics at meso-level, (b) Moment versus curvature of the Twintex fabric through a loading-unloading cycle.

In the current work, the bending behavior of a dry thermoplastic woven fabric, made up of co-mingled E-glass/Polypropylene yarns (under the commercial name Twintex TPP60N22P-060) is investigated using a new custom test set-up. The plain weave samples with the size of 2×3 yarns ($\sim 1\text{cm}$ by $\sim 1.5\text{cm}$) were prepared and mounted on the cyclic bending test device (Figure 1) where, once the gripper is fixed and the fabric undergoes pure bending, the load cell reads the reaction force due to the movement of the other gripper rotating on a circular path. The distance between the grippers is fixed at 1cm . The device provides the angle of rotation, and thereby, curvature can be calculated approximately by

$$2\varphi/d \approx 1/R = \kappa \quad (1)$$

where R , φ , d and κ are the radius, angle of rotation, gauge length and curvature, respectively.

In this experimental method, speed and angle of rotation are controlled by the servo motor, and the gauge length can be assigned by re-arranging the grippers in the specific length. A load cell measures the reaction force. Moreover, the rotating jaw is capable of moving up to $\pm\pi/2$ in a circular path ensuring pure bending deformation. Based on the formula provided in Eq. (1), it is feasible to derive the curvature directly from the device, considering the fact that the sample is small enough to have a circular deformation profile. The thermoplastic pre-preg samples tested were dry, i.e. in an unconsolidated state, cut and prepared from the fabric rolls. Each sample was in the same condition prior to the test; all samples were tested at room temperature, and they were not under a pre-tension/compression prior to the test and filaments were checked to ensure that they were not damaged. The center of samples is always set to be the center of the rotation of the bending arm. Gauge lengths in these experiments were set to be constant at 1cm . The moment is captured during the pure bending deformation. The obtained moment-curvature curve (Figure 1) clearly illustrated a hysteresis behavior of the fabric. The bending rigidity, i.e. the slope of the moment-curvature curve, of the woven fabric varies through the loading-unloading condition.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A meso-level FE model of the above bending test was recently established in Abaqus (Figure 2), where the yarns geometry was modelled directly via Python scripting using a sinusoidal function presented in [14]. In order to determine the material parameters for the yarns, an iterative inverse method was utilized to achieve optimum parameters of the hyper-elastic and Mullin effect [13], by comparing the reaction forces obtained from the simulations with those measured by the bending device. More specifically, in the parameter identification process, the maximum force during loading-unloading regime, and the nonlinear response during unloading were compared iteratively with the simulation until a good agreement was found. The contact friction coefficient at crossovers was tested separately and was found to be 0.35.

It is worth noting that an appropriate yarn material model for the current application needed to consider (i) the nonlinear mechanical behavior during loading and (ii) the energy ‘loss’ during unloading regime. The above-mentioned Mullin effect model is deemed capable of meeting these key aspects. The model was compared with the experiments as shown in Figure 2. The results showed that the FE model is able to capture the dissipation of energy through the loading-unloading regime accurately.

Figure 2: Comparison of experiments and FE simulation: (a) the fabric sample and FE model, (b) curvature ($R^2 = 97.30\%$), (c) reaction forces ($R^2 = 73.84\%$), (d) moment-curvature curves (dissipated energy for experiment and simulation are 3.59N.mm/mm and 1.91N.mm/mm respectively).

3.1 Sensitivity analysis

In this sub-section, we study the effect of friction coefficient (μ) and angle of rotation (θ ; in radians) as well as the yarn material bending rigidity (i.e. tuned through Mullin effect parameters) on the resulting nonlinear bending behavior of a unit cell of the fabric as shown in Figure 3. The same material model and boundary conditions in the previous section (i.e. similar to the bending set-up) was applied to this representative unit cell. A Python script was written to automatically run 24 combinations of friction and angle of rotation.

A close inspection of the obtained results (Figure 4) showed that the effect of angle of rotation on the reaction forces is significant. On the contrary, the effect of frictional interaction of yarns through the unit cell was insignificant compared to the effect of yarn bending stiffness. The results demonstrated that by doubling the angle of rotation/curvature (i.e. sharper forming angle), the moment triples. By increasing the material stiffness by 25%, compared to the control material (i.e. based on the best match to experiments), the moment increased by almost 33%. In these graphs, ‘Stiffer’ material refers to the yarn with 25% increased stiffness compared to the control case.

Figure 3: Schematic of the unit cell using Python script in Abaqus. The dimensions: $h=0.7\text{mm}$, $s=5\text{mm}$, $w=2\text{mm}$ were measured using a Micro-CT scan of the actual sample shown in Figure 3a.

Finally, to study the aforementioned effects on the dissipated energy (N.mm/mm) magnitude (net area under the moment-curvature curve); we analyzed the data using R programming within the framework of using a full factorial (mixed-level) design of experiments (see **APPENDIX**). According to the results in Table 1 and Figure 5, it can be concluded that the effect of bending angle and yarn material rigidity are clearly significant (P-values<5%) on the level of dissipated energy. All the interaction parameters were found to be insignificant in this case study, which means for material design purposes, the selection of yarn material can be used to enhance the bending behavior of the fabric regardless of its interactive effect with the friction parameter, or the level of curvature to be endured.

Figure 4: Effect of friction, angle of rotation and material rigidity during the bending of the unit cell. (a) Effect of angle of rotation (in radians) on the control material calibrated through experiments with constant coefficient of friction. (b) Effect of angle of rotation (in radians) on the stiff material (25% stiffer than the control material). (c) Effect of coefficient of friction through cyclic loading on the representative unit cell for both control and the stiff material. (d) Comparison of the reaction forces against curvature for both materials under various angle of rotations.

Table 1. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the effect of parameters under cyclic bending of the representative unit cell.

Factors	DOF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F	P-Value
Friction	2	0.23	0.11	0.55	0.6035
Bending Angle	3	198.85	66.28	331.40	4.7115e-7
(Yarn) Material	1	1.52	1.52	7.60	0.03299
Friction× Bending Angle	6	1.20	0.20	1.0	0.5
Friction× Material	2	0.21	0.11	0.55	0.6035
Bending Angle× Material	3	1.03	0.34	1.70	0.2654
Error=Friction× Bending Angle× Material	6	1.17	0.20		
Total	23	204.21			

Figure 5: Individual and interacting effects of friction, angle of rotation (in radians) and yarn material rigidity on the dissipated energy (N.mm/mm) level through loading-unloading bending regime (a) summary of effect of parameters on the dissipated energy (N.mm/mm) through cyclic loading. This figure illustrates the significant effect of angle of rotation on the dissipated energy in contrast to lower effect of material and coefficient of friction. (b) Interaction of coefficient of friction and angle of rotation on the dissipated energy. (c) Interaction of friction and material on the dissipated energy (N.mm/mm). (d) Interaction of material and angle of rotation on the dissipated energy (N.mm/mm) though loading-unloading regimes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The multi-scale nature of composite fabrics has been often overlooked, especially under out-of-plane bending deformations. In particular, due to the presence of fiber twist, geometrical non-linearities, crimp and undulation, and dominant friction and shearing between filaments within yarns and between yarns at cross overs, the irreversible behavior of the fabrics during forming regimes are likely. Consequently, in this work a numerical model was employed at the meso-level to investigate anti-plane deformation of a typical dry thermoplastic woven fabric under a loading-unloading bending cycle. The effect of friction and angle of rotation (curvature) as well as the yarn bending rigidity on the resulting nonlinear bending stiffness of the fabric unit-cell was analyzed. The yarn material model used was hyper-elastic that included “Mullin effect”, which is known to account for the nonlinear behavior of the materials through cyclic loadings. The base model (i.e. control) was calibrated against the experimental data. The analysis showed that the effects of curvature and yarn material rigidity are significant. Frictional interaction at crossovers is found to yield approximately 5% of the relative energy dissipation through one load cycle based on the moment– curvature curves. The yarn material rigidity for any given curvature was found to be significant statistically, while all other interaction parameters were insignificant.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The financial support from the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NSERC) of Canada is gratefully acknowledged. The authors would also like to acknowledge CRN students and visiting scholars, in particular Ms. B. Khatir, for their great contribution to the development of the fabric-bending device.

APPENDIX

Table A1. Factors and their levels used in the design of experiments.

RUN#	INPUT: FACTORS			OUTPUT: ENERGY LOSS (N.mm/mm)
	Yarn Material	Friction coefficient	Bending Angle (radian)	
1	Control	0.1	0.52	0.4171
2	Control	0.2	0.52	0.4178
3	Control	0.3	0.52	0.4186
4	Control	0.1	0.78	1.2904
5	Control	0.2	0.78	1.2913
6	Control	0.3	0.78	1.2921
7	Control	0.1	1.04	2.8074
8	Control	0.2	1.04	2.8111
9	Control	0.3	1.04	2.8116
10	Control	0.1	1.5	7.3444
11	Control	0.2	1.5	7.3491
12	Control	0.3	1.5	7.3640
13	Stiffer	0.1	0.52	0.4850
14	Stiffer	0.2	0.52	0.4874
15	Stiffer	0.3	0.52	0.4920
16	Stiffer	0.1	0.78	1.5864
17	Stiffer	0.2	0.78	1.6204
18	Stiffer	0.3	0.78	1.6372
19	Stiffer	0.1	1.04	3.3934
20	Stiffer	0.2	1.04	3.5501
21	Stiffer	0.3	1.04	2.8074
22	Stiffer	0.1	1.5	7.3444
23	Stiffer	0.2	1.5	8.6982
24	Stiffer	0.3	1.5	9.5658

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Komeili, A. S. Milani *Finite element modeling of woven fabric composites at meso-level under combined loading modes* InTech, 2011.
- [2] A. Charmetant, J. G. Orliac, E. Vidal-Sallé, P. Boisse, Hyperelastic model for large deformation analyses of 3D interlock composite preforms, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, No. 12, 2012, pp. 1352-60.
- [3] A. Willems, S. V. Lomov, I. Verpoest, D. Vandepitte, Drape-ability characterization of textile composite reinforcements using digital image correlation, *Optics and Lasers in Engineering*, **47**, No. 3, 2009, pp. 343-51.
- [4] G. Hivet, A. V. Duong , A contribution to the analysis of the intrinsic shear behavior of fabrics, *J Composite Mater*, **45**, 6, 2011, pp. 695-716, (doi: 10.1177/0021998310382315).
- [5] F. Abbassi, I. Elfaleh, S. Mistou, A. Zghal, M. Fazzini, T. Djilali , Experimental and numerical investigations of a thermoplastic composite (carbon/PPS) thermoforming, *Struct Control Health Monit*, **18**, 7, 2011, pp. 769-80, (doi: 10.1002/stc.491).
- [6] F. T. Peirce. , 26—THE “HANDLE” OF CLOTH AS A MEASURABLE QUANTITY, *Journal of the Textile Institute Transactions*, **21**, 9, 1930, pp. T416, (doi: 10.1080/19447023008661529).
- [7] B. Liang, P. Chaudet, P. Boisse , Curvature determination in the bending test of continuous fibre reinforcements, *Strain*, **53**, 1, 2016, pp. e12213, (doi: 10.1111/str.12213).
- [8] D. Soteropoulos, K. Fetfatsidis, J. A. Sherwood, J. Langworthy. ,Digital Method of Analyzing the Bending Stiffness of Non-Crimp Fabrics, *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2011, AIP, pp. 913-917.
- [9] H. Alshahrani, M. Hojjati, Bending behavior of multilayered textile composite prepregs: Experiment and finite element modeling, *Materials & Design*, **124**, 2017, pp. 211-24.
- [10] S. Kawabata. , The Standardisation and Analysis of Hand Evaluation'The Hand Evaluation and Standardisation Committee, *The Textile Machinery Society of Japan*, 1980, .
- [11] T. A. Martin, D. Bhattacharyya, I. F. Collins, Bending of fibre-reinforced thermoplastic sheets, *Composites Manufacturing*, **6**, No. 3, 1995, pp. 177-87.
- [12] P. Boisse, J. Colmars, N. Hamila, N. Naouar, Q. Steer, Bending and wrinkling of composite fiber preforms and prepregs. A review and new developments in the draping simulations, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **141**, 2018, pp. 234-49.
- [13] J. Diani, B. Fayolle, P. Gilormini , A review on the Mullins effect, *European Polymer Journal*, **45**, 3, 2009, pp. 601-12.
- [14] T. M. McBride, J. Chen , Unit-cell geometry in plain-weave fabrics during shear deformations, *Composites Sci Technol*, **57**, 3, 1997, pp. 345-51.